

Smart Use of Novel Digital Tools for advanced performance and reduced costs in CSP tower plants

SUN-DT PLATFORM

SUN-DT will advance and integrate four interoperable innovative digital tools — **HELIOSTATACC** (automatic heliostat calibration and characterisation), **SUN-DTWIN** (automated decision-making of the solar field and receiver), **D-OPT** (energy management and dispatch optimisation), and **PREDOM** (predictive operation and maintenance) — into a unified **SUN-DT Platform**, which will be tested and validated at two experimental facilities and two commercial plants, representing different CSP tower configurations.

DEMONSTRATORS

Cerro Dominador's CSP plant with O&M services provided by ACCIONA

Khi Solar One CSP plant owned by a consortium led by COX, with O&M services provided by COX

DLR's Solar Towers Jülich

IMDEA Energy's Very High Concentration Solar Tower

CONSORTIUM

MORE INFORMATION

[linkedin.com/company/sun-dt/](https://www.linkedin.com/company/sun-dt/)

x.com/SUN_DT_Project

cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101234781

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